

1 **HPV E2 activates ROR1.**

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6 HPV E2 is the viral transcriptional activator but likely has a multitude of functions separate from the
7 E1-associated viral trans-activation event that remain undefined. We demonstrate here by ectopic
8 expression of HPV E2 in human cells and measurement of total transcription following next generation
9 RNA-sequencing activation of *Ror1* by human papillomavirus E2 protein.

8 Citations

9 1. Widhopf, G.F., Cui, B., Ghia, E.M., Chen, L., Messer, K., Shen, Z., Briggs, S.P., Croce, C.M. and
10 Kipps, T.J., 2014. ROR1 can interact with TCL1 and enhance leukemogenesis in E μ -TCL1 transgenic
11 mice. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 111(2), pp.793-798.

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